

USE MATH FUN TRICKS FOR ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Sharipova Guloy

Bekchanova Nilufar

Urgench State University teachers

Annotation: *This article focuses on effective, modern, and innovative didactic games and math tricks in teaching mathematics to increase pupils interest in learning mathematics in the primary grades.*

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Today, in the age of scientific and technological progress, mathematics plays an important role, so in the last decades, the curriculum of school mathematics has been changed several times. A new methodological system for mathematics has been developed for the new DTS and program. The methodology of teaching mathematics is primarily aimed at teaching and educating young pupils in the general system.

A necessary and important condition for effective teaching is the control over the pupils' mastery of the subject being studied. Didactics has developed various methods of its implementation, including oral questioning of pupils; control and independent work; inspection of household items, tests, testing using technical means. In didactics, the use of one or another method of control, depending on the course, the age of the pupils, etc., as well as the methodology of control are sufficiently developed.

Independent and control work in the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary school, effective means of conducting individual written surveys of pupils. Some didactic materials are designed to cover a limited range of program topics, while others are designed to cover all major topics in an elementary school math course.

Some didactic materials (especially those for low-intensity schools) contain more teaching materials, while others contain more control materials.

Many practical reforms in the field of exact sciences are taking place in our country today

is being carried out. In particular, the development of mathematics and the younger generation

It is a field of broader interpretation, deeper training from an early age scientists and representatives are in the spotlight.

In this sense, mathematical problems and examples are simple and clear to young people

This will be a great impetus for the future of the industry.

Such mathematical tricks were used to teach pupils mathematics will be of interest if held before the start of a new topic helps pupils focus.

The point of this trick is that it depends on the size of your shoes depending on your age. The question is how. for this we can find out by doing the following sequence.

Step 1: Increase the size of your shoes by 5;

Step 2: Add 13 to the product;

Step 3: Multiply the sum by 20;

Step 4: Subtract your year of birth from the product;

Step 5: Add the number 1760 to the subtraction;

Step 6: If you draw a line in the middle of the result, the right side is your age, the left

The size of your shoes will be formed.

For example, my shoe size is 40. How old am I?

Is it because

$$40 * 5 = 200$$

$$200 + 13 = 213$$

$$213 * 20 = 4260$$

$$4260 - 1994 = 2266$$

$$2266 + 1760 = 4026$$

$$40/26$$

It turned out that I was 26 and my shoes were 40.

Let's check now:

$$2020 - 1994 = 26 \text{ years}$$

So we conclude that it turned out to be correct.

Note: The number 1760 in step 5 is only for 2020 as the number increases year by year

increases. For example, next year, in 2021, it is necessary to use the number 1761 in the trick.

FIND THE NUMBER THAT SOMEONE ELSE THINKS.

This distracting "trick" is familiar to many, but if it is presented to young children, they will not be surprised, so do it: Think of a number, add to it the next number. Add 7 to the result and divide by 2. Now subtract the number you guessed from the resulting number. Answer 4 came out, right?

How to do it:

Think of a number: for example, 52

Add the next number to the number you think: $52 + 53 = 105$

Add 7 to it: $105 + 7 = 112$

Divide by 2: $112/2 = 56$

Subtract the number you think: $56 - 52 = 4$ (answer 4)

If you still do not understand the essence of this "trick", in this example, no matter what number one thinks, the answer is added to the number you add (in our example, it is the number 7), and the number is divided by two. , if you say add 9 to the number one thinks, the final answer is 5 $((9+ 1) / 2)$, if you say add 3, the answer is 2 and so on.